

Can an odd perfect number be triangular?

Reduction to Pell-type equations with an arithmetic constraint

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Abstract

We investigate whether an odd perfect number (OPN) can simultaneously be a triangular number. Starting from Euler's canonical form $N = p^\alpha m^2$, we derive a complete case analysis that reduces the problem to four Pell-type equations in which an additional arithmetic constraint — that a coordinate of the Pell solution must itself be a perfect square or p^α times a perfect square — is imposed. We also record the intersection of Touchard's congruence conditions with the residues of odd triangular numbers modulo 36, which severely restricts the admissible residue classes. We raise three precise questions concerning prior literature, local obstructions, and computational feasibility.

Problem statement

We investigate the possibility that an odd perfect number (OPN) might also be a triangular number. Starting from Euler's form for OPNs, we obtain a reduction to four Pell-type equations (or variants thereof), together with a supplementary arithmetic constraint that appears to be quite restrictive. We ask whether this reduction is already known in the literature, and whether there exist immediate local arguments that could rule it out.

1 Starting hypothesis and notation

Let N be an odd perfect number. By Euler's theorem,

$$N = p^\alpha m^2,$$

where p is the *special prime* satisfying $p \equiv \alpha \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$ and $\gcd(p, m) = 1$.

Suppose further that N is triangular:

$$N = T_n = \frac{n(n+1)}{2}.$$

Since N is odd, T_n is odd, which forces $n \equiv 1$ or $2 \pmod{4}$.

2 Coprime factorization of T_n

Case n even

Write $n = 2k$. Then

$$T_n = k(2k+1), \quad \gcd(k, 2k+1) = 1.$$

Case n odd

Write $n = 2k + 1$. Then

$$T_n = (2k + 1)(k + 1), \quad \gcd(2k + 1, k + 1) = 1.$$

In both cases $T_n = u \cdot v$ with $\gcd(u, v) = 1$.

3 Using the perfect condition

Because p^α is the only factor appearing with an odd exponent in the factorization of N , the entire factor p^α must divide exactly one of u or v ; the other factor must be a perfect square. Writing

$$A = p^\alpha a^2, \quad B = b^2,$$

with $\gcd(a, b) = 1$ and $p \nmid ab$, and examining the four parity-times-assignment possibilities yields:

Case $n = 2k$ (even)

$$(1) \quad b^2 - 2p^\alpha a^2 = 1. \tag{1}$$

$$(2) \quad p^\alpha a^2 - 2b^2 = 1. \tag{2}$$

Case $n = 2k + 1$ (odd)

$$(3) \quad 2b^2 - p^\alpha a^2 = 1. \tag{3}$$

$$(4) \quad b^2 - 2p^\alpha a^2 = -1. \tag{4}$$

Equations (1) and (4) are standard Pell equations $x^2 - Dy^2 = \pm 1$ with $D = 2p^\alpha$. Since $\alpha \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, α is odd, so p^α is not a perfect square and therefore D is not a perfect square. Equations (2) and (3) are generalized variants.

4 The crucial arithmetic constraint

Finding solutions (x, y) to the above equations is insufficient. One additionally requires that the coordinate corresponding to x be a perfect square (i.e. $x = b^2$) or equal to p^α times a square (i.e. $x = p^\alpha a^2$). This is a very strong arithmetic condition on the Pell solutions.

5 Other useful known constraints

- **Touchard's theorem (1953).** An OPN satisfies $N \equiv 1 \pmod{12}$ or $N \equiv 9 \pmod{36}$. The odd triangular residues modulo 36 are $\{1, 3, 9, 15, 21, 25, 27, 31\}$; intersecting with Touchard's congruences leaves only 1 and 9. Hence

$$T_n \equiv 1 \text{ or } 9 \pmod{36}.$$

- **Euler's conditions.** $p \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, $\alpha \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$.
- **Size.** The coprime factors have order $\approx \sqrt{N}$, so $b \approx N^{1/4}$, useful for numerical searches combined with known lower bounds on N .

6 Open questions

1. Has this reduction — together with the constraint that the x -coordinate of the Pell solutions must be a square or p^α times a square — already appeared in the literature on OPNs?
2. Are there elementary local arguments (modulo small primes such as 3, 4, 8, 5, 9, 11, ...) that rule out any of the four equations, or that show the condition “ x is a square” is impossible in those cases?
3. Is a direct computational search feasible: fix p and α satisfying $p \equiv \alpha \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, solve $x^2 - 2p^\alpha y^2 = \pm 1$ via continued fractions, and test the “ x is a square” condition? What are the known theoretical and practical bounds on p, α that would make such a search meaningful?

Keywords: odd perfect numbers, triangular numbers, Pell equations, Diophantine equations, number theory.